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OPHTHALMIC SOLUTION FORMULATION OF A PROSTAGLANDIN ANALOGUE FOR TREATING GLAUCOMA

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ABSTRACT

Glaucoma is a progressive, neurodegenerative optic nerve disease that can cause significant visual morbidity and affects over 60 million people worldwide. The latest marketed product in the form of ophthalmic solution to treat the glaucoma is RESCULA[®] which utilizes a novel prostaglandin analogue, Unoprostone Isopropyl as active ingredient at 0.15% w/v. Characterization by laser diffraction of the marketed product revealed the drug product in the nano emulsion form. The API, Unoprostone Isopropyl is a clear colorless viscous oily liquid, practically insoluble in water and poorly permeable. The formulation utilized 1% Polysorbate 80 as solubilizer; 0.05% Disodium Edetate as preservative, chelating agent and antioxidant; 0.015% Benzalkonium Chloride as preservative; 4.3% Mannitol as osmotic agent; Sodium Hydroxide / Hydrochloric Acid at quantity sufficient for pH adjustment. The final product was sterilized through filtration using polyvinylidene filters. The filtrate was packed in Low Density polyethylene bottle with dropper insert capped with High Density Polyethylene closure. The stability of the product was evaluated and found to be stable in both upright and horizontal position at ICH recommended accelerated stability condition of 40°C / 25% RH.

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INTRODUCTION

Unoprostone Isopropyl is a prostaglandin analogue indicated for lowering of elevated intraocular pressure (IOP) in patients with open-angle glaucoma or ocular hypertension¹. Unoprostone Isopropyl is a clear colourless viscous oily liquid, practically insoluble in water and poorly permeable². The challenging aspect is to formulate the insoluble oily API into solubilized ophthalmic solution. The brand / reference / marketed product, RESCULA[®] available in the market comprises 1.5 mg Unoprostone Isopropyl, 0.015% Benzalkonium Chloride, Mannitol, Polysorbate 80, Edetate Disodium, Sodium Hydroxide, Hydrochloric Acid and Water For Injection packed in bottle, dropper tip made of Low Density Polyethylene and caps made of polypropylene polymer³. In this research, drug product was designed utilizing brand listed ingredients and ensured comparable Physico-chemical attributes and stability to that of the marketed product. Moreover to achieve cost effectiveness, the finalized composition was stabilized and packed in bottle, dropper tip made of Low density polyethylene and caps made of cheaper and widely available HDPE polymer. Glaucoma is a progressive, neurodegenerative optic nerve disease that can cause significant visual morbidity and affects over 60 million people worldwide⁴. By making a cost-effective generic ophthalmic solution of Unoprostone Isopropyl, it will impart greater benefit by reducing the intraocular hypertension thereby restoring the eye sight of diseased population at large.

RESEARCH JUSTIFICATION

The research was aimed to provide a cost effective alternative to the marketed product RESCULA[®] that utilizes a novel prostaglandin analogue, Unoprostone Isopropyl for the treatment of Glaucoma.

LITERATURE

Youmin Wang and team investigated the stability of an ophthalmic solution formulation of Unoprostone isopropyl (UI), a prostaglandin like compound, in two types of packaging materials, polypropylene (PP) and low-density polyethylene (LDPE)⁵. Remo Susanna Jr and team reviewed the recent literature available on the clinical efficacy of prostanoids namely Latanoprost and Unoprostone Isopropyl as well as the studies directly comparing these drugs⁶. Patents relevant to synthesis, method of uses of the drug product and composition of the drug product includes US 5001153, US 5151444, US 5166178, US 5212200, US 5208256, US 5221763, US 6458836 and US 6770675⁷.

PURPOSE / OBJECTIVE

The objective is to develop an ophthalmic solution of Unoprostone Isopropyl, 0.15% w/v which would be comparable to the marketed product, RESCULA[®] with respect to physico-chemical properties and stability characteristics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS:

Unoprostone Isopropyl from Yonsung Fine Chemicals; Mannitol from Roquette; Polysorbate 80, Edetate Disodium, Sodium Hydroxide and Hydrochloric Acid from Avantor Performance Materials; Benzalkonium Chloride from FeF Chemicals; LDPE dropper bottles, LDPE dropper inserts and HDPE closures from Clinicare;

EQUIPMENTS / INSTRUMENTS:

Osmometer of Fisher Scientific; Dissolved Oxygen Meter of Hanna Instruments; Stopwatch of Casio; Micro & Ultramicro balance of Mettler Toledo; Viscometer of Brookfield; Particulate Counter of Particulate Measuring Systems; Malvern Zetasizer of Malvern Instruments; Aseptic Filtration System of Merck Millipore; 0.22 micron PVDF Filter and Filter Cartridge of Merck Millipore; Laminar Flow Hood of Krishna Scientific Suppliers; Sonicator of Fisher Scientific; Nitrogen Cylinder with gauge & Oxygen Cylinder with gauge of DC Ranganathan Agency; Photostability chamber, 40°C / 75% RH stability chamber, -20°C Stability chamber, 55°C Stability chamber, 30°C / 65% RH Stability Chamber, 2-8°C Stability chamber, 40°C / 75% RH stability chamber, Hot Air Oven and Autoclave of Thermolab Scientific Equipments; Microscopic Particle Count using SMZ-168-TP Motic Trinocular Stereomicroscope equipped with MT3i camera, PM-LED illuminator and IMT i-solution software; HPLC of Waters; UV Spectrophotometer of Shimadzu; FTIR of Thermofisher; pH Meter of Hanna Instruments and Lab Stirrer of Remi Motors.

METHODS:

Sterility test, Osmolality & Osmolarity, pH, Viscosity, Particle Size Distribution, Preservative Efficacy Testing, Water Conductivity, Deliverable Volume, Minimum Fill, Particulate Matter, Specific Gravity, Light diffraction measurement of particle size, Anti-microbial agents content, Pyrogen test, Bacterial Endotoxin test, Antimicrobial effectiveness testing, Visible particulates, Method of Analysis of Mannitol, Edetate Disodium, Benzalkonium Chloride and Polysorbate 80 were done as per USP.

SERVICES UTILIZED:

Filter validation study was done at Merck Millipore. Leachable / Extractable evaluation of packing components was done at Clinicare.

EXPERIMENTATION

API CHARACTERIZATION:

Unoprostone Isopropyl was characterized with respect to Appearance, Water, Related Substances, Assay and Solubility.

MARKETED PRODUCT CHARACTERIZATION:

The marketed product was characterized for quantitative amounts of in-actives viz Mannitol, Polysorbate 80, Edetate Disodium, Benzalkonium Chloride by HPLC; Appearance, Fill Volume, Drop weight, pH, Specific gravity, Osmolality, Viscosity, Buffering Capacity, Preservative Content, Microscopic Particle Count, Assay, Related Substances, Particle Size, Zeta Potential Conductivity and Packaging configuration.

PROTOTYPE FORMULATION & OVERAGE REQUIREMENT:

API being an oily liquid there is a chance of loss of API during weighing and formulation. To evaluate the overage requirement 2 batches were made with and without 5% overage of API.

FORMULATION OF PROTOTYPES:

In about 3/4th of the stated quantity of Sterile Water For Injection Mannitol, EDTA Disodium, Benzalkonium Chloride and Polysorbate 80 were dissolved and the pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.75 ± 0.75 with 1N NaOH or 1N HCl and then API was dissolved in the pH adjusted solution and finally the volume was made up with Sterile Water For Injection. Then the whole solution was filtered through 0.22 micron PVDF filter. The whole activity was carried out under aseptic environment in Laminar Flow Hood. The prototypes were evaluated for Description, Assay (Before & after filtration), Related Substances and pH. The samples were also stability evaluated for the same tests mentioned.

MANUFACTURING PROCESS OPTIMIZATION:

The batch size of the drug product was scaled up from 250 mL batch size (Prototype) to 6000 mL batch size. The final filtered drug product was characterized for the following studies.

MANUFACTURING PROCESSING CONDITION:

To study the effect of oxygen on the product and to evaluate the need of inert atmosphere during the processing conditions, experiments were carried out to compare the effects of oxygen and nitrogen; one batch was purged with nitrogen and another with compressed air. The samples were analyzed for assay and impurity profile.

pH OPTIMIZATION STUDY:

The pH range proposed for the finished product is 5.75 ± 0.75 . Trials were manufactured with the bulk pH adjusted at the lower side (5.0) and higher side (6.5) of pH range. Both the batches were monitored for assay and impurities.

PHOTO STABILITY STUDY:

Photo stability study was conducted for the test product and the time required for the given exposure standards are as given below:

- A. 15 Hours exposure equivalent to visible light
- B. 6 Hours equivalent exposure to UV Light

The marketed product, RESCULA® is supplied in sterile low-density polyethylene bottle with a low-density polyethylene dropper tip, a turquoise polypropylene closure in a pack size of 7.5 ml. The test formulation was filled in sterile low density polyethylene bottle with a low density polyethylene dropper tip and high density polyethylene closure in a pack size of 7.5 ml for photo stability. The bottles were placed in horizontal position to achieve maximum exposure of the light. The comparison of the exposed sample and Initial sample with respect to the impurities was done.

STABILITY OF PRODUCT TO VARYING TEMPERATURE:

To evaluate the effect of temperature variations during transport of the drug product, the formulation was subjected to temperature excursion. Following are the temperature conditions for the products that may be exposed to subfreezing temperature variations and at higher temperature variations:

- Temperature excursion at subfreezing temperature ($-20^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 2 days and incubated at long-term storage condition ($2^{\circ}\text{C}-8^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 1 day and evaluated for Description, pH, Assay and Related Substances.
- Temperature excursion at high temperature ($40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C} / 75\% \pm 5\% \text{RH}$) for 2 days and incubated at long-term storage condition ($2^{\circ}\text{C}-8^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 1 day and evaluated for Description, pH, Assay and Related Substances.
- Temperature excursion at subfreezing temperature ($-20^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 2 days and incubated at long-term storage condition ($25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C} / 60\% \pm 5\% \text{RH}$) for 1 day and evaluated for Description, pH, Assay and Related Substances.
- Temperature excursion at high temperature ($55^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 2 days and incubated at long-term storage condition ($25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C} / 60\% \pm 5\% \text{RH}$) for 1 day and evaluated for Description, pH, Assay and Related Substances.

STABILITY OF PRODUCT WHEN IN-USE:

The study was done as Initial (0 Day); 7th day of bottle opening (As per the dosing regimen, procedure to include wasting 2 drops every day up to 7th day and conducting the study on 7th day); 4 weeks interval (procedure to include wasting 2 drops every day upto 7th day, testing on 7th day, further incubation without wasting any drop and testing on 4th week). The samples were analyzed for physicochemical properties like Description, pH, Assay, Degradation Products, Antimicrobial Effectiveness and Microbial Contamination. Test intervals: This study is conducted at the initial life stage of product incubated at $25^{\circ}\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/60\%\pm 5\% \text{RH}$.

EVALUATION OF COMPARATIVE PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MARKETED PRODUCT AND TEST PRODUCT:

The proposed formulation was also studied for pH, Specific Gravity, Osmolality, Viscosity, Buffering Capacity, Microscopic Particle Count, Particle Size, Zeta potential, Conductivity and Drop weight and compared with the marketed product.

HOLD TIME STUDY:

A study was conducted by holding the final filtered solution in a type-I glass vessel at room temperature for 0 hours, 12 hours, 24 hours and 48 hours. The solution was characterized for Physico-chemical and bio-load at the end of 0th hour and 48th hour. Bio-load was evaluated at the end of 12th and 24th hour.

ANTIMICROBIAL EFFECTIVENESS TESTING / PRESERVATIVE EFFICACY STUDY:

Based on the label claim of the marketed product RESCULA[®], the quantity of Benzalkonium Chloride used as a preservative is 0.015% w/v. In order to evaluate the preservative effectiveness, antimicrobial challenge was performed using 50%, 60% and 75% the label claim of preservative and the samples were subjected to stability study at 25[±]2°C/60[±]5% RH for 0th day, 7th day, 14th day & 28th day and evaluated for Assay of Benzalkonium Chloride, Assay of drug content and Antimicrobial effectiveness testing / preservative efficacy study.

FILTER VALIDATION STUDY:

The filter validation study comprises Product Bubble Point Study, Compatibility Study and Bacterial Retention Study.

PRODUCT BUBBLE POINT STUDY:

The Bubble point determination studies of sterilizing grade (0.22 micron) hydrophilic Durapore[®] membrane wetted with Unoprostone Isopropyl Ophthalmic Solution 0.15% was performed. Sterilizing Grade (0.22 micron) hydrophilic Durapore[®] membranes with a filtration surface area of 13.8 cm² were used to determine the minimum bubble point for this product. The purpose of this study is to check the filter integrity by means of bubble point determination. Test Specifications: Sterilizing grade (0.22 micron) hydrophilic Durapore[®] membrane. Minimum standard bubble point with pure water: ≥ 50 psi (23°C). Temperature: The test measurements with purified water were done at 22 ± 4°C and Unoprostone Isopropyl Ophthalmic Solution 0.15% were done at 20-25°C.

FILTER COMPATIBILITY STUDY:

The compatibility study of the sterilizing grade (0.22 micron) hydrophilic Durapore[®] membrane with Unoprostone Isopropyl Ophthalmic Solution 0.15% was performed. Sterilizing-grade (0.22 micron) hydrophilic Durapore[®] membranes with a filtration surface area of 13.8 cm² were used for the tests. The filter compatibility study comprised of four elementary tests: Bubble point variation determination, Flow rate variation determination, membrane mass variation determination and visual examination. The study used one lot of product and each elementary test is performed on three different filters from the same lot. The study was performed over 11.11 hours of soaking period of the filters in Unoprostone Isopropyl Ophthalmic Solution 0.15%. Test Specifications: Sterilizing grade (0.22 μm) hydrophilic Durapore[®] membrane Minimum standard bubble point with pure water ≥ 50 psi (23°C). Temperature: The test measurements with purified water were done at 22 ± 4°C and Unoprostone Isopropyl Ophthalmic Solution 0.15% were done at 20-25°C.

BACTERIAL RETENTION STUDY:

The purpose of this study is to provide *Brevundimonas diminuta* American Type Culture Collection (ATCC) 19146 retention data for 0.22 μm Durapore[®] membrane after exposure to Unoprostone Isopropyl Ophthalmic Solution 0.15%. 47 mm discs with a filtration surface area of 13.8 cm² were used for the Unoprostone Isopropyl Ophthalmic Solution 0.15% membrane bacterial retention validation study. The *Brevundimonas diminuta* challenge inoculums was inhibited by Unoprostone Isopropyl Ophthalmic Solution 0.15% as demonstrated in the viability study. Therefore, a modified test was performed. The test filters were conditioned with sterile product, rinsed and challenged with Saline Lactose Broth. A final portion of the rinse filtrate was assayed and proven not to be bactericidal to *Brevundimonas diminuta*.

LEACHABLE/ EXTRACTABLE STUDY OF PACKAGING COMPONENTS:

The summary of study results of leachable / extractable study in different day in different media was studied and reported.

STABILITY STUDY:

The finalized product was stability evaluated at accelerated condition, 40°C / 25%RH in both horizontal and upright orientation and the details were reported.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

API CHARACTERIZATION:

From the API characterization, Table.1 it is evident that the API is an oily liquid and is practically insoluble in Water.

MARKETED PRODUCT CHARACTERIZATION:

Based on the tabulated information, in Table.2 it was decided to develop the formulation matching the appearance and Physico-chemical properties of the marketed product, RESCULA[®] (Unoprostone Isopropyl Ophthalmic Solution) 0.15%.

PROTOTYPE FORMULATION & OVERAGE REQUIREMENT:

To evaluate the overage requirement 2 batches of 250 mL batch size were made with (Table.3) and without 5% overage (Table.4) of API. From the tabulated data it is evident that there is no need for 5% overage requirement for formulation.

MANUFACTURING PROCESS OPTIMIZATION:

The batch size of the drug product was scaled up from 250 mL batch size (Prototype) to 6000 mL batch size (Table.5). In this batch nitrogen purging was done before and after API addition to reduce the dissolved oxygen level in the solution. The final filtered drug product was characterized for the further optimization study evaluation.

MANUFACTURING PROCESSING CONDITION:

From the Table.6 results it is evident that no significant difference between oxygen purged batch and nitrogen purged batch.

pH OPTIMIZATION STUDY:

From the Table.7 results it is evident that the product was found to be stable between pH 5.0 to 6.5.

PHOTO STABILITY STUDY:

From the Table.8 results it is evident that the product was found to be stable with the selected packaging configuration i.e. low density polyethylene bottle with a low density polyethylene dropper tip and high density polyethylene closure.

STABILITY OF PRODUCT TO VARYING TEMPERATURE:

- The results of the Temperature excursion at subfreezing temperature ($-20^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 2 days and incubated at long-term storage condition ($2^{\circ}\text{C}-8^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 1 day is shown in Table.9.
- The results of the Temperature excursion at high temperature ($40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C} / 75\% \pm 5\% \text{RH}$) for 2 days and incubated at long-term storage condition ($2^{\circ}\text{C}-8^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 1 day is shown in Table.10.
- The results of the Temperature excursion at subfreezing temperature ($-20^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 2 days and incubated at long-term storage condition ($25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C} / 60\% \pm 5\% \text{RH}$) for 1 day is shown in Table.11.
- The results of the Temperature excursion at high temperature ($55^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 2 days and incubated at long-term storage condition ($25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C} / 60\% \pm 5\% \text{RH}$) for 1 day is shown in Table.12.

The results of temperature excursion studies confirm the stability of the samples at various temperature and incubation conditions, as there is no significant change in Assay, pH and Impurity values.

STABILITY OF PRODUCT WHEN IN-USE:

From the Table.13 results it is evident that the physicochemical parameter of Unoprostone Isopropyl Ophthalmic Solution 0.15% was found to be stable upto 4 weeks after storage at $25 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C} / 60\% \pm 5\% \text{RH}$, once the bottle was pierced.

EVALUATION OF COMPARATIVE PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF RESCULA[®] AND TEST PRODUCT:

From the Table.14 results it is evident that the physico-chemical property of the developed product was found to be comparable to the marketed product, RESCULA[®].

HOLD TIME STUDY:

From the Table.15 results it is evident that the manufactured ophthalmic solution can be kept on hold for about 48 hours from the time of initiation of manufacture before packaging.

ANTIMICROBIAL EFFECTIVENESS TESTING/ PRESERVATIVE EFFICACY STUDY:

From the Table.16 results it is evident that the trial batches with preservative concentration of 50%, 60% and 75% of the label claim passes the preservative efficacy test (i.e. sample is sufficiently preserved), implying the test product is sufficiently preserved at Benzalkonium Chloride concentrations of 0.015% w/v.

FILTER VALIDATION STUDY:

The following were the studies done as part of filter validation study. Since the product is sterilized by filtration method, the integrity of the filter used for filtration is essential for ensuring the sterility of the drug product.

PRODUCT BUBBLE POINT STUDY:

The Bubble Point Ratio (BPR) of (0.22 microns) hydrophilic Durapore® membrane wetted with Unoprostone Isopropyl Ophthalmic Solution 0.15% at 20-25° is equal to 0.580. The product bubble point specifications of the (0.22 micron) hydrophilic Durapore® membrane wetted with Unoprostone Isopropyl Ophthalmic Solution 0.15% at 20-25°C is: Minimum product bubble point specification = Minimum Standard Bubble Point X BPR = 50 X 0.58 = 29 psi.

FILTER COMPATIBILITY STUDY:

Bubble Point Variation: 0.311%. Flow Rate Variation: 2.241%. Membrane Mass Variation: 0.37367%. Visual Examination: No Significant visible discoloration, swelling, shredding or dissolution of the test filter has been observed. Given the test results, it concluded that Millipore's sterilizing grade (0.22 µm) Hydrophilic Durapore® membrane are not affected by the Unoprostone Isopropyl Ophthalmic Solution 0.15% for a contact period of about 11.11 hours at 20-25°C.

BACTERIAL RETENTION STUDY:

The sterilizing grade filter demonstrated acceptable performance, as the membrane retained the *Brevundimonas diminuta* challenge concentration of equal to or greater than 1 X 10⁷ cfu/cm² of effective filtration area. The *Brevundimonas diminuta* challenge organism passed through the 0.45 µm filter indicating that it was appropriately sized during test. Sterility of the test system was demonstrated by the absence of microbial growth on the assay filter downstream of the 0.22 µm test filters.

LEACHABLE / EXTRACTABLE STUDY OF PACKAGING COMPONENTS:

From the Table.17 results it is evident that Magnesium was found to be extracted / leached with the maximum of about 255 parts per billion under stress condition. No Polynuclear aromatics / Antioxidants / Benzothiazoles found to leach or get extracted. Hence the final product can be safely packaged in the selected dropper bottle-nozzle system.

STABILITY STUDY:

The final product was stability evaluated at accelerated condition, 40°C / 25%RH in both horizontal (Table.18) and upright (Table.19) orientation. Based on the tabulated results, it is clear that the developed drug product is stable at accelerated condition, 40°C / 25%RH in both horizontal and vertical orientation for about 3 months.

TABLE 1. API CHARACTERIZATION.

Appearance	Colourless to pale yellow oil
Related Substances	
Any other impurity	Not detected
Total impurities	Not detected
Assay	99.9%
Solubility	Practically insoluble in Water Freely soluble in Acetonitrile Ethanol, 2-Propanol, Ethyl Acetate, Diethyl Ether, 1,4-Dioxane and Hexane

TABLE 2. MARKETED PRODUCT CHARACTERIZATION.

Particulars	Results
Brand Name	RESCULA [®] 0.15%
Generic Name	Unoprostone Isopropyl Ophthalmic Solution, 0.15% w/v
Manufacturer	Manufactured for: Sucampo Pharma Americas, LLC. Bethesda, MD 20814, Made in Japan
Label Claim	Each mL contains: 1.5 mg of Unoprostone Isopropyl; Benzalkonium Chloride 0.015% is added as preservative.
Storage	Store between 2°C-25°C (36°-77°F)
Pack	Sterile low-density polyethylene bottle with a low-density polyethylene dropper tip and a turquoise Polypropylene closure.
Excipients	Mannitol, Polysorbate 80, Edetate Disodium, Sodium Hydroxide or Hydrochloric Acid (to adjust pH) and Water for injection. Mannitol: 4.3%
Quantitative details of Excipients (Reverse Engineering By HPLC)	Polysorbate 80: 1.0% Benzalkonium Chloride: 0.015% Edetate Disodium: 0.05%
Appearance	Clear colorless solution
Fill Volume	5 mL
Drop Weight	Average drop weight is 33.695 mg (Range: 31.12 mg to 35.31 mg)
pH	Average is 5.8 (Range: 5.6 to 5.9)
Specific Gravity	Average is 1.02532 (Range: 1.00592 to 1.04725)
Osmolality	Average is 245.3 mOsm/kg (243 mOsm/kg to 248 mOsm/kg)
Viscosity	Average is 1 cps [Spindle no. 21; 100 RPM]
Buffering Capacity	0.5 mL (Range: 0.5 mL to 0.5 mL)
Preservative Content (%)	101.4 (Benzalkonium Chloride)
Microscopic Particle Count	> 10 microns NMT 20 Particles > 25 microns NMT 5 Particles
Related Substances (%)	
Individual Unknown Impurity	0.249
Total Impurities	0.691
Assay (%)	103.7
Particle Size	19.90 nm
Zeta Potential	4.88 mv
Conductivity	0.302 µs/cm

TABLE 3. PROTOTYPE FORMULATION WITH OVERAGE.

S.No	Ingredients	mg / mL	With 5% Overage		
			g / batch		
1	Unoprostone Isopropyl	1.50	0.394*		
2	Mannitol	43.00	10.750		
3	Polysorbate 80	10.00	2.625*		
4	Benzalkonium Chloride	0.15	0.0375		
5	EDTA Disodium	0.50	0.125		
6	Sodium Hydroxide	Adjust the pH to 5.75±0.75	Adjust the pH to 5.75±0.75		
7	Hydrochloric Acid	Adjust the pH to 5.75±0.75	Adjust the pH to 5.75±0.75		
8	Sterile Water For Injection	Adjust to 1 mL	Adjust to 250 mL		
	Assay before filtration		105.92		
	Assay after filtration		106.36		
	Tests		Initial	2-8°C- 1 month	30°C/65%RH -1 month
	Description		Clear colorless solution		
	pH Limit		6.1	6.0	6.1
	Assay		106.4	107.7	101.7
	Highest Unknown Impurity		0.018	0.238	0.332
	Total Impurity		0.041	0.439	0.997

*Note: 5% overage taken.

TABLE.4 PROTOTYPE FORMULATION WITHOUT OVERAGE.

S.No	Ingredients	mg/ mL	Without 5% Overage		
			g / batch		
1	Unoprostone Isopropyl	1.50	0.375		
2	Mannitol	43.00	10.750		
3	Polysorbate 80	10.00	2.500		
4	Benzalkonium Chloride	0.15	0.0375		
5	EDTA Disodium	0.50	0.125		
6	Sodium Hydroxide	Adjust the pH to 5.75±0.75	Adjust the pH to 5.75±0.75		
7	Hydrochloric Acid	Adjust the pH to 5.75±0.75	Adjust the pH to 5.75±0.75		
8	Sterile Water For Injection	Adjust to 1 mL	Adjust to 250 mL		
	Assay before filtration		100.29		
	Assay after filtration		100.18		
Tests		Initial	2-8°C - 1 month	30°C/65%RH -1 month	
	Description		Clear colorless solution		
	pH Limit	6.0	6.1	6.1	
	Assay	100.2	100.7	98.1	
	Highest Unknown Impurity	0.026	0.257	0.341	
	Total Impurity	0.048	0.462	1.107	

TABLE.5 COMPOSITION FOR 6 LITRE BATCH SIZE FOR OPTIMIZATION STUDY.

S.No	Ingredients	g/ batch			
1	Unoprostone Isopropyl	9.00			
2	Mannitol	258.00			
3	Polysorbate 80	60.00			
4	Benzalkonium Chloride	0.90			
5	EDTA Disodium	3.00			
6	Sodium Hydroxide	Adjust the pH to 5.75±0.75			
7	Hydrochloric Acid	Adjust the pH to 5.75±0.75			
8	Sterile Water For Injection	Adjust to 6000 mL			
Tests		Initial	2-8°C 3 months	30°C / 65%RH 3 months	
	Description		Clear colorless solution		
	pH	5.9	6.1	5.9	
	Assay	102.9	99.2	96.2	
	Highest Unknown Impurity – NMT 1.0%	ND	0.362	0.518	
	Total Impurities	ND	0.477	0.760	

TABLE.6 MANUFACTURING PROCESS CONDITION STUDY.

Tests	Initial	With Oxygen Purging		With Nitrogen Purging	
		40°C/75%RH 24 hours	55°C 24 hours	40°C/75%RH 24 hours	55°C 24 hours
Highest Unknown Impurity	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Total Impurity	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Assay	102.9	100.3	103.1	102.8	102.3

TABLE.7 pH OPTIMIZATION STUDY.

Tests	pH 5.0	pH 6.5
Description	Clear colorless solution	
Preservative Content (Benzalkonium Chloride)	97.9	98.1
Highest Unknown Impurity	ND	ND
Total Impurity	ND	ND
Assay	100.2	100.1

ND – Not Detected.

TABLE.8 PHOTO STABILITY STUDY.

Tests	Initial	Photo Exposed
Description	Clear colorless solution	
Highest Unknown Impurity	ND	ND
Total Impurity	ND	ND
Assay	102.9	99.8

ND – Not Detected.

TABLE.9 STABILITY OF PRODUCT TO VARYING TEMPERATURE.

(-20°C ± 5°C) for 2 days followed by (2°C-8°C) for 1 day		
Tests	Before Excursion	After Excursion
Description	Clear colorless solution	
pH	5.9	6.1
Highest Unknown Impurity	ND	ND
Total Impurity	ND	ND
Assay	102.9	99.9

ND – Not Detected.

TABLE.10 STABILITY OF PRODUCT TO VARYING TEMPERATURE.

(40°C ± 2°C / 75% ± 5% RH) for 2 days followed by (2°C-8°C) for 1 day		
Tests	Before Excursion	After Excursion
Description	Clear colorless solution	
pH	5.9	6.0
Highest Unknown Impurity	ND	ND
Total Impurity	ND	ND
Assay	102.9	101.7

ND – Not Detected.

TABLE.11 STABILITY OF PRODUCT TO VARYING TEMPERATURE.

(-20°C ± 5°C) for 2 days followed by (25°C ± 2°C / 60% ± 5%RH) for 1 day			
Tests		Before Excursion	After Excursion
Description		Clear colourless solution	
pH		5.9	5.9
Highest Unknown Impurity	NMT 1.0%	ND	ND
Total Impurity	NMT 3.0%	ND	ND
Assay	90.0-110.0%	102.9	100.9

ND – Not Detected.

TABLE.12 STABILITY OF PRODUCT TO VARYING TEMPERATURE.

(55°C ± 2°C) for 2 days followed by (25°C ± 2°C / 60% ± 5%RH) for 1 day		
Tests	Before Excursion	After Excursion
Description	Clear colorless solution	
pH	5.9	6.1
Highest Unknown Impurity	ND	ND
Total Impurity	ND	ND
Assay	102.9	95.9

ND – Not Detected.

TABLE.13 IN-USE STABILITY STUDY.

In-Use Stability Study				
Tests		Initial 0 th Day	7 th Day	4 th Week (28 Days)
	Description	Clear colorless solution		
	pH	5.9	6.0	6.0
	Highest Unknown Impurity	ND	ND	ND
	Total Impurity	ND	ND	0.013
	Assay of Benzalkonium Chloride	99.5	99.2	99.5
	Assay of Unoprostone Isopropyl	102.9	97.7	98.1
Antimicrobial Effectiveness	Escherichia coli	1 X 10 ⁶ cfu / mL	6.7 LR	6.6 LR
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	1 X 10 ⁵ cfu / mL	6.6 LR	6.5 LR
Testing	Staphylococcus aureus	1 X 10 ⁶ cfu / mL	6.4 LR	6.4 LR
	Candida albicans	1 X 10 ⁵ cfu / mL	-	-
Test For Microbial Contamination	Aspergillus niger	1 X 10 ⁵ cfu / mL	-	-
	Escherichia coli			
	Salmonella sp			
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	Absent	Absent	Absent
	Staphylococcus aureus			
	Clostridia sp			
	Candida albicans			

ND – Not Detected; LR – Log Reduction; CFU – Colony Forming Units; Compendia specification for Antimicrobial Effectiveness: Bacteria: Not less than 1.0 log reduction from the initial calculated count at 7 days, not less than 3.0 log reductions from the initial count at 14 days, and no increase from the 14 days' count at 28 days. Yeast & Molds: No increase from the initial calculated count at 7, 14, and 28 days.

TABLE.14 COMPARATIVE PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS.

S.No	Parameters	RESCULA®	Test Product
1	pH	5.8 (Range: 5.6-5.9)	5.8 (Range: 5.8-5.8)
2	Specific Gravity	1.03 (Range: 1.00-1.05)	1.02 (Range: 1.01-1.02)
3	Osmolality	245.3 mOsm/kg (243 mOsm/Kg-248 mOsm/Kg)	248 mOsm/kg (247 mOsm/Kg-249 mOsm/Kg)
4	Viscosity	Average is 1 cps [Spindle no. 21; 100 RPM]	Average is 1 cps [Spindle no. 21; 100 RPM]
5	Buffering Capacity	0.5 mL (Range: 0.5 mL to 0.5 mL)	0.9 mL (Range: 0.9 mL to 1.0 mL)
6	Microscopic Particle Count	> 10 microns NMT 20 Particles > 25 microns NMT 5 Particles	> 10 microns NMT 20 Particles > 25 microns NMT 5 Particles
7	Particle Size	19.90 nm	22.97 nm
8	Zeta Potential	4.88 mV	3.51 mV
9	Conductivity	0.302 µs/cm	0.266 µs/cm
10	Drop Weight (mg)	33.695 mg (31.12 mg to 35.31 mg)	40.455 mg (39.19 mg to 41.77 mg)

TABLE.15 HOLD TIME STUDY.

Hold Time Study					
Tests	Initial	12 th Hour	24 th Hour	48 th Hour	
Description	Clear colorless solution				
pH	5.9	6.1	6.0	6.1	
Highest Unknown Impurity	ND	ND	ND	ND	
Total Impurity	ND	ND	ND	ND	
Assay of Benzalkonium Chloride	99.5	98.4	99.1	99.3	
Assay	102.9	101.9	100.7	100.9	
Test For Microbial Contamination	Escherichia coli				
	Salmonella sp				
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent
	Staphylococcus aureus				
	Clostridia sp				
	Candida albicans				

ND – Not Detected.

TABLE.16 ANTIMICROBIAL EFFECTIVENESS TESTING / PRESERVATIVE EFFICACY STUDY.

Preservative Content	Tests	Initial	7 th day	14 th day	28 th day
50%	Assay (Benzalkonium Chloride)	53.13	53.2	53.1	53.0
	Assay (Unoprostone Isopropyl)	99.7	99.4	100.1	99.8
	Antimicrobial Effectiveness	Complies	Complies	Complies	Complies
60%	Assay (Benzalkonium Chloride)	59.80	59.5	59.9	60.1
	Assay (Unoprostone Isopropyl)	100.1	100.0	99.7	100.1
	Antimicrobial Effectiveness	Complies	Complies	Complies	Complies
75%	Assay (Benzalkonium Chloride)	75.60	75.1	75.2	75.5
	Assay (Unoprostone Isopropyl)	101.1	100.8	99.2	99.7
	Antimicrobial Effectiveness	Complies	Complies	Complies	Complies

Compendia Specification for Antimicrobial Effectiveness: Bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* & *Staphylococcus aureus*): Not less than 1.0 log reduction from the initial calculated count at 7 days, not less than 3.0 log reductions from the initial count at 14 days, and no increase from the 14 days' count at 28 days. Yeast & Molds (*Candida albicans* & *Aspergillus niger*): No increase from the initial calculated count at 7, 14, and 28 days.

TABLE.17 LEACHABLE / EXTRACTABLE STUDY OF PACKAGING COMPONENTS.

Instruments Used	Media	Results (in ppb)		
		Day 0	Day 14	Day 28
Elements by ICP-MS	Water media	BQL	BQL	Mg-128.06
	Formulation media	BQL	Mg-166.30	Mg-254.97
PNA'S by GC-MS/MS	Water media	BQL	BQL	BQL
	Formulation media	BQL	BQL	BQL
Antioxidants & UV absorbers & Benzothiazoles by LC-MS/MS	Water media	BQL	BQL	BQL
	Formulation media	BQL	BQL	BQL

BQL-Below Quantification Limit.

TABLE.18 ACCELERATED STABILITY STUDY – UPRIGHT ORIENTATION.

40°C / 25%RH – Upright Orientation					
Tests	Initial	1 month	2 month	3 month	
Description		Clear colorless solution			
pH	6.1	6.0	6.0	6.0	
Osmolality (mOsm / L)	263	265	267	270	
Particulate Matter (Particle per mL)	NMT 50 particles / mL ≥ 10 μm	4.33	4.27	4.28	4.29
	NMT 5 particles / mL ≥ 25μm	0.27	0.25	0.28	0.26
Assay		102.1	101.2	100.1	101.3
Benzalkonium Chloride Content		97.4	98.9	98.2	98.8
Disodium Edetate Content		102.4	101.7	101.2	102.1
Related Substances	Highest Unknown Impurity	ND	ND	ND	0.3
	Total Impurity	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.6
Sterility	No microbial growth	No microbial growth	No microbial growth	No microbial growth	
		0.6%	1.2%	1.2%	
		0.6%	1.1%	1.1%	
Weight Loss	-	1.1%	1.9%	2.0%	
		0.6%	1.1%	1.2%	
		0.6%	1.3%	1.1%	

ND – Not Detected.

TABLE.19 ACCELERATED STABILITY STUDY – HORIZONTAL ORIENTATION.

40°C / 25%RH – Horizontal Orientation					
Tests	Initial	1 month	2 month	3 month	
Description	Clear colorless solution				
pH	6.0	5.9	6.1	6.0	
Osmolality (mOsm / L)	268	266	265	263	
Particulate Matter (Particle per mL)	NMT 50 particles / mL ≥ 10 µm	4.31	4.30	4.29	4.32
	NMT 5 particles / mL ≥ 25µm	0.29	0.28	0.31	0.30
Assay	101.1	102.1	101.3	100.9	
Benzalkonium Chloride Content	99.2	98.1	99.7	99.9	
Disodium Edetate Content	100.7	101.2	100.9	100.8	
Related Substances	Highest Unknown Impurity	ND	ND	ND	0.2
	Total Impurity	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.5
Sterility	No microbial growth	No microbial growth	No microbial growth	No microbial growth	No microbial growth
		0.8%	1.4%	1.8%	
		0.9%	1.3%	1.9%	
Weight Loss	-	1.0%	1.3%	1.8%	
		0.7%	1.4%	1.8%	
		0.9%	1.4%	1.9%	

ND – Not Detected.

CONCLUSION

An ophthalmic solution of Unoprostone Isopropyl, 0.15% w/v was successfully formulated and was found to equivalent to the marketed product, RESCULA[®] with respect to composition, physico-chemical characteristics and stability. The manufacturing process was completely optimized and necessary precautions were taken with respect to order of mixing of ingredients, environment condition, sterilization by filtration etc to make a stabilized drug product of Unoprostone Isopropyl.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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